

The COMPRESSION of MICROSTRUCTURE and MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR of CASTING and POWDER PROCESSING of SiC_P REINFORCED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The microstructure and deformation characteristic of casting and powder metallurgy (PM) MMCs have been investigated. The model materials are casting SiC particulate reinforced aluminium alloy A356, casting Al_2O_3 particulate reinforced aluminium alloy 6061 and powder metallurgical SiC particulate reinforced aluminium alloy 6061. The materials investigated contained 10 % and 20 % by volume of reinforced particulates, and heat treated to peak aging.

In general, the distribution of SiC particle of PM specimens are more uniform than the casting ones. The tensile strength and stiffness of the composites are higher than the unreinforced matrix alloys in all types of the composites with the powder metallurgical SiC particulate reinforced $Al - 6061$ has the highest tensile strength. On the other hand, the elongation of the unreinforced matrix alloys are much higher than MMCs with the casting Al_2O_3 particulate reinforced $Al - 6061$ composites are higher than others composites. The test results demonstrate the importance of the composite microstructure on the mechanical behaviour of the composites. Moreover, matrix yielding and particle cracking are found on the fracture surfaces of the composites.

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) have been developed in the last few years, in order to reduce the weight of components in structural applications and to improve their thermal and mechanical properties. Most of the recent research work on MMCs has focused on aluminum as the matrix metal. The properties of light weight, environmental resistance and good mechanical performance have made aluminum alloys very popular. Among the different types of reinforcement, particulate reinforced aluminum alloys have high potential for investigation and development. Their main advantages are that they can be manufactured and processed

using traditional methods; also their physical properties are reasonably isotropic. Because of their low cost and ease of formability, they have potential uses in many applications[1].

The low ductility of MMCs is the primary obstacle preventing their applications[2-4]. The presence of brittle particles, metal oxides and intermetallic precipitates, tends to reduce their ductility and fracture toughness. The influence of matrix microstructure and the morphology of the reinforcement on the strain to failure of particulate reinforced MMCs is still not very clear. Continuing research is needed to overcome these deficiencies. The study focuses on experimental observations of the effects of material processing, matrix microstructure and reinforcement morphology on the uniaxial stress-strain response of particulate reinforced MMCs in order to better understand the effect of the composite microstructure on the mechanical behaviour and the failure mechanisms of the composites.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The material behaviour of MMCs depends on fabrication route and subsequent thermomechanical treatment. The microstructure and mechanical property of different fabrication routes of the MMCs have been selected to study.

MATERIALS FABRICATION

Production techniques of metal matrix composites include diffusion bonding, vapour deposition and plasma spraying for continuous fibre composites, and compocasting, melt infiltration and standard powder metallurgical processing for particulate reinforced composites[1]. The experimental materials used in this investigation were manufactured using casting *SiC* particulate reinforced aluminium alloy A356, casting Al_2O_3 particulate reinforced aluminium alloy 6061 and powder metallurgical *SiC* particulate reinforced aluminium alloy 6061.

Compocasting (or stir-casting), involves the addition of the reinforcing particles into a stirred melt of metal matrix. The melt is poured into a mould, then undergoes secondary processing as a wrought billet. The control of particle spatial distribution and wetting of the particle-matrix interface are the keys to produce a good bond [5]. The choice of potential matrix alloys is limited by the need to prevent reactions between the reinforcement and the molten matrix which are in contact at high temperatures for long periods [6].

Melt infiltration (or squeeze-casting), is performed by pouring the matrix alloy into a die cavity containing a preform of reinforcing phase, usually held together by an organic binder which is burnt off later. The die applies a pressure, normally by a hydraulic ram. The applied pressure and ram displacement can be monitored and operated in a controlled atmosphere [7,8].

The standard powder metallurgical processes have included vacuum hot pressing and extrusion. The matrix material was an argon gas atomised *Al* – 6061. These powders were blended dry with three commercially available grades of C6 quality silicon carbide grit of nominal size 10 μm . Composites of 10 and 20% volume fractions were manufactured.

The heat treatment to increase the strength of the specimens was a three step process [9]:

1. solution heat treatment: dissolution of soluble phases at 550°C for two hours in argon atmosphere,
2. quenching: development of supersaturation state in cold water,
3. ageing: precipitation of solute atoms at elevated temperature, artificial aging at 177°C in oil bath for four hours for peak-ageing.

After heat treating, all specimens were tested for hardness to confirm their precipitation hardening properties and to set up the specimen hardness database.

A convention for labelling the different composite systems is marked. Each system will be given a label of the form: volume fraction/particle size/ heat treatment/matrix alloy. For example, 10/3/T6/6061 corresponds to an aluminum-1 % magnesium matrix containing 10 % by volume of 3 μm *SiC* particles which have been quenched and peak aged.

MICROSTRUCTURAL CHARACTERISTICS

Optical microscopy and transmission electron microscopy techniques were used to characterise the material.

Typical transverse micrographs of the composites containing *SiC* particles are shown in Figure 1. In general, the distribution of *SiC* particle of PM specimens are more uniform than the casting ones. These pictures show that while the spatial distribution of particles appeared homogeneous, it was still quite clumped. These results also showed the particles to be like irregular blocks rather than platelets or cubes.

The grain structure of the composite was revealed by electro-chemical etching on the PM specimens. The grains in the centre of the transverse section were equiaxed, but at the specimen edge the grains were elongated. The grain size of the unreinforced control alloys was about 200 μm , but the grain size of the 10/10/PA/6061 was about 80 μm . A transmission electron micrograph of an interface in the composite is shown in Figure 2. No significant interface layer was observed.

TENSILE TESTING

Tensile tests to failure were performed on the composites and unreinforced control alloys. Tests were carried out on an Instron 4204 at a strain rate of $7.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. A redesigned clip gauge was used to extend the specimen deformation to failure. The analogue strain and load data were stored in a transient recorder, then converted to digital data and transferred to a personal computer. The results were analysed to show the effect of the microstructural parameters on elastic modulus, 0.2% proof stress, ultimate stress, fracture stress and work-hardening rate. Their effect on elongation and area reduction have also been investigated.

The stiffness, strength and elongation of different fabrication routes and volume fractions of particulate reinforced MMCs are shown in Figure 3. In general, the addition of the reinforcing particles causes increases in the stiffness and the ratio of tensile to yield stress, but decreases the strain to failure. The tensile strength and stiffness of the composites are higher than the unreinforced matrix alloys in all types of the composites with the powder metallurgical *SiC* particulate reinforced Al - 6061 has the highest tensile strength. On the other hand, the elongations of the unreinforced matrix alloys are much higher than MMCs with the casting Al_2O_3 particulate reinforced Al - 6061 composites are higher than others composites.

Scanning electron microscopic examination of the fracture surfaces revealed a dimpled fracture surface for both the unreinforced and reinforced specimens. The fracture surface of the unreinforced alloy specimen contained an even distribution of large dimples connected by sheets of smaller dimples, as shown in Figure 4 (a). It indicated a pattern resulting from microvoid nucleation, growth, coalescence and failure. Figure 4 (b) shows the fracture surface of the 10/10/PA/6061 specimen. Besides particle cracking, particle pullout sometimes observed. The pulled out particles were coated with aluminium matrix. The failure mode of the reinforced composites was predominantly through matrix ductile failure due to stress concentration near the interface region. Particle cracking occurs because of the triaxial

stresses and plastic strain near the brittle particle surface. Some particle pullout is seen due to the matrix failure.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The factors which affect the mechanical properties of particulate reinforced MMCs may include :

- Fabrication route,
- Mechanical working and secondary processing,
- Matrix microstructure,
- Morphology and the volume fraction of the reinforcing particles.

The present fabrication routes for producing particulate reinforced MMCs are limited to powder metallurgy and casting techniques. Utilizing the PM approach, both *SiC* whisker and particulate reinforcements with a wide variety of matrix materials can be produced. The casting MMC's are limited to using *SiC* particulate reinforcements in standard aluminum casting alloys with high silicon level (A356 and A357), and Al_2O_3 reinforcements in wrought alloys with low silicons level (2124 and 6061) [10].

The microstructure of MMCs is complex with contributions from the matrix materials, the reinforced phases and interfacial reactions. In particulate reinforced MMCs, the incorporation of significant quantities of ceramic particles into an alloy, combined with mechanical processing, tend to produce a matrix of fine grain size. In the present study, the grain size of the matrix of the 10/10/PA/6061 was bigger than the particle interspacing. The grain diameter was about $80 \mu m$, and each contained several particles in the grain boundary. Moreover, powder route processing also produced oxide particles within the matrix in addition to any age hardening precipitates.

The interfacial strength is significantly affected by alloy chemistry and reinforcement type. It controls the load transfer between the metal matrix and ceramic reinforcement. In *SiC* particulate reinforced aluminum composite, the interfacial bond has been measured as of the order of $1.2 GPa$ [22], which is much higher than the expected strength of both the matrix material and the reinforced particle. In the present study, no significant interface layer was observed.

The tensile properties of particulate reinforcement MMCs has been studied. The important findings is the stiffness and tensile stress of composites increase with increasing reinforcement volume fraction. However, more strengthening effects may be involved if the material is given an appropriate thermal treatment, such as aging treatment. The precipitates are no longer discrete but maintain some special coherence with the matrix and have structural effects beyond their own volume. Coherent precipitates are normally cut by dislocations. Coherency strains or misfit dislocations also interact with deformation dislocations and can tend to extra strengthening. Adding up the effects of grain size and previous working which also relate to matrix alloys, more complex strengthening mechanisms are shown in particulate reinforced MMCs.

The PM fabrication route can produce a more homogeneous distribution of *SiC* reinforced particles, better stiffness and tensile strength compared to casting route. But with lower cost and net-shape casting, the casting fabrication route keeps impetus in the research and development of the MMCs, particularly for the A356 and A357 premium casting alloys reinforced with *SiC* particles.

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Figure 1: Transverse micrograph of (a) PM (b) Casting MMCs.

Figure 2: An interface in the 10/3/PA/6061 of PM composite.

Tensile Test Stiffness

Figure 3: The stiffness of PM and casting particulate reinforced MMCs.

Tensile Test Tensile Strength

Figure 4: The strength of PM and casting particulate reinforced MMCs.

Tensile Test Elongation

Figure 5: The elongation of PM and casting particulate reinforced MMCs.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6: The fracture surface of the tensile specimen from (a) an unreinforced alloy and (b) 20/10/PA/6061.